

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

MILLIY BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH MAQSADLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH JAHON TAJRIBASI VA O‘ZBEKISTON UCHUN ECHIMLAR BO‘YICHALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

Toshmurotov Abdusattor Qobulovich

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi biznes va tadbirkorlik oliy maktabi talabasi

Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlari (BRM) 2015 yilda BMT Bosh Assambleyasining 70-sessiyasida qabul qilingan va 2030 yilga qadar amalga oshirilishi kerak bo‘lgan global iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va ekologik barqarorlikka erishishni maqsad qilgan 17 ta yo‘nalish va 169 ta aniq maqsaddan iborat. Bu maqsadlar rivojlangan va rivojlanayotgan davlatlar uchun ham muhim bo‘lib, ularning moliyalashtirilishi global iqtisodiyotning barqaror va barqaror taraqqiyoti uchun asosiy shartdir. O‘zbekiston uchun ham BRMga erishish muhim bo‘lib, unga erishishda moliyalashtirish strategiyalarini to‘g‘ri tanlash va jahon tajribasidan foydalanish kerak.

Jahon tajribasida barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini moliyalashtirish

Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini moliyalashtirish jarayonida jahonning turli mamlakatlari turli yondashuvlar va strategiyalarni qo‘llaydilar. Bunday tajribalarda asosiy e‘tibor investitsiyalar, xalqaro moliya manbalari va davlat siyosatining o‘zaro integratsiyasini ta‘minlashga qaratilgan.

Xalqaro moliya institutlari va donorlar

Moliyalashtirishning eng asosiy manbalari xalqaro moliya institutlari, xususan, BMT, Svet banki, Xalqaro valyuta jamg‘armasi (XVJ) va Evropa qayta tiklash va taraqqiyot banki (EQTB) hisoblanadi. Ular BRMlarni amalga oshirish uchun grantlar, kreditlar va investitsiyalarni taqdim etishadi. Bunday moliyalashtirishning afzalligi shundaki, u rivojlanish maqsadlariga erishish uchun zarur resurslarni taqdim etadi va kobul qilingan davlatlarning moliyaviy bosimini kamaytiradi.

Xususiy sektor va investitsiyalar

Jahon tajribasida barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini amalga oshirish uchun xususiy sektorning roli muhim. Xususiy investorlar, banklar va kapital bozorlar barqaror investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda muhim o‘rin tutadi. Masalan, Evropadagi ko‘plab mamlakatlar barqaror moliyalashtirishning asosiy manbai sifatida "yashil" obligatsiyalarni chiqarishgan. Bu obligatsiyalar ekologiyaga oid loyihalarni moliyalashtirishda yordam beradi.

Davlatning moliyalashtirish va rejalashtirish funksiyalari

Jahonda davlatlar moliyalashtirishni tashkiliy va strategik jihatdan yo‘naltirish uchun barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini o‘z milliy taraqqiyot dasturlari bilan integratsiya qilishgan. Davlatlar barqaror rivojlanishga oid loyihalarga byudjetni yo‘naltirish, soliq siyosatini o‘zgartirish va iqtisodiy dasturlar ishlab

chiqishga qaratilgan. Masalan, Koreya va Yaponiya davlatlari ekologik toza texnologiyalarga investitsiyalarni jalb qilish uchun soliq imtiyozlari va subsidiyalar ta'lim etishgan.

O'zbekiston uchun barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini moliyalashtirish: Echimlar va imkoniyatlar

O'zbekiston, jahon tajribasidan foydalangan holda, barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini moliyalashtirishda birqator strategiyalar ishlab chiqishi kerak. Bu strategiyalar quyidagi yo'nalishlar bo'yicha amalga oshirilishi mumkin:

Xalqaro moliya manbalari va donorlardan foydalanish

O'zbekiston barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlarini moliyalashtirishda xalqaro moliya institutlari bilan hamkorlikni mustahkamlash va donorlarni jalb qilishga alohida e'tibor qaratish zarur. Xalqaro banklar, investitsiya tashkilotlari va donor mamlakatlardan grantlar, arzan kreditlar va texnologik yordam olish orqali moliyalashtirish hajmini oshirish mumkin.

Mahalliy moliya manbalari va xususiy sektorni jalb qilish

O'zbekistonda xususiy sektorning rivojlanishi, shuningdek, "yashil" iqtisodiyotga qaratilgan investitsiyalar ahamiyatli bo'lmoqda. Davlat, xususiy sektorni moliyalashtirishga jalb etish uchun soliq imtiyozlari va xavf-xatarni kamaytirish uchun yangi mexanizmlar yaratishi kerak. Xususiy kompaniyalar, davlat va xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikda "yashil" iqtisodiyotni moliyalashtirish orqali, ekologik barqarorlikni ta'minlash mumkin.

Moliyaviy ishonch va mahalliy banklar rolini oshirish

O'zbekistonda mahalliy banklar va moliya institutlari barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga erishishda markaziy o'rin tutadi. Bu banklar ekologiyaga va ijtimoiy rivojlanishga yo'naltirilgan loyihalarga kreditlar ajratish va mablag'larni jamlashda faol ishtirok etishi mumkin. Shuningdek, mahalliy moliya bozorlarini rag'batlantirish uchun davlatning moliyaviy mexanizmlarini kuchaytirish va investitsiya muhitini yaxshilash zarur.

Soliq siyosati va byudjetni yo'naltirish

O'zbekistonda davlatning byudjet siyosati barqaror rivojlanishga yo'naltirilgan bo'lishi kerak. Davlat BRMga yo'naltirilgan loyihalar uchun moliyalashtirishda yagona strategiyani ishlab chiqishi kerak. Masalan, ekologik toza energetika, barqaror aholi yashash sharoitlari va ijtimoiy barqarorlikka yo'naltirilgan subsidiyalar va soliq imtiyozlari qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Moliyalashtirish va jamg'armalar tuzish

O'zbekiston o'zining milliy taraqqiyot maqsadlari uchun alohida jamg'armalar tuzishi va ular orqali barqaror rivojlanishga yo'naltirilgan loyihalarni moliyalashtirish imkoniyatiga ega. Bunday jamg'armalar xorijiy va mahalliy investorlardan mablag'lar jalb qilishi va qishloq xo'jaligi, yoshlar ta'limi va infratuzilmani rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilishi mumkin.

Xulosa

Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga erishishda moliyalashtirish muhim rol o'ynaydi. Jahon tajribasidagi ko'pgina davlatlar moliyalashtirish manbalarini

diversifikatsiyalash, xususiy sektorni jalb qilish, xalqaro moliya institutlaridan foydalanish va ekologik, ijtimoiy barqarorlikka yo'naltirilgan investitsiyalarni jalb qilishni amalga oshirgan. O'zbekiston uchun eng samarali yo'l — bu xalqaro va mahalliy moliya manbalarini integratsiyalash, ekologik va ijtimoiy loyihalarga davlat va xususiy sektorni jalb qilish hamda barqaror moliyalashtirish mexanizmini yaratishdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Narkuziyev A. HUDUDLARDA INFRATUZILMANI RIVOJLANTIRISH RESURS SALOHİYATI MOHIYATI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14619154> //International scientific and practical conference. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 10-13.
2. Narkuziyev A. KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY INFRATUZILMA KO'RSATKICHLARINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14619344> //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 14-22.
3. Narkuziyev A. O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK UCHUN INFRATUZILMANI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14619146> //International scientific and practical conference. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 3-9.
4. Narkuziyev A. O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATI UCHUN ISHLAB CHIQRISH INFRATUZILMASINI YAXSHILASHNING ASOSIY TENDENSIYALARI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14619202> //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2025. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 5-13.
5. Narkuziyev A. TURKIYA VA XITOIY HUDUDLARIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SOHASI UCHUN INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA O'ZBEKISTON XAM TAJRIBALARDAN INNAVATSION USULDA FOYDALANISH: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14375391> //Journal of International science networks. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 3. – C. 130-143.
6. Quvvatov G. et al. 2023-YIL SOLIQ QONUNCHILIGIDAGI KIRITILGAN O'ZGARTISHLARNING DAVLAT BYUDJETIGA VA IQTISODIYOTGA TA'SIRI //International Journal of scientific and Applied Research. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 10-15.
7. Narkuziyev A., Baxriddinov Y. IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNI TASHKIL ETISHNING YANGI SHAKLI SIFATIDA TARMOQ IQTISODIYOTINING XUSUSIYATLARI //International Journal of scientific and Applied Research. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 51-55.
8. Rustamovich N. A. ROLE OF INFRASTRUCTURE TO DEVELOP SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 9. – C. 412-416.
9. Narkuziyev A., Umurzaqova S. O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI HUDUDLARIDA ICHKI RESURLARDAN SAMARALI INNAVATSION USULDA FOYDALANISHNING MUHIM AHAMIYATI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 46-58.
10. Narkuziyev A., Umurzaqova S. KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI //Science technology&Digital finance. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 3. – C. 40-47.
11. Narkuziyev A., Muxtarov F., Qarshiboyev Z. TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KORXONALARNING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //International Journal of scientific and Applied Research. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 33-36.
12. Quvvatov G., Norquzivev A. O'ZBEKISTONDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'I MA'MURCHILIGI AMALIYOTI, YUTUQLARI VA KAMCHILIKLARI, UNI SODDALASHTIRISH VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI //International Journal of scientific and Applied Research. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 4-9.